

汽车车身先进设计制造 国家重点实验室

State Key Laboratory Of Advanced Design And Manufacturing For Vehicle Body

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Study on the low-velocity impacting responses and residual properties of sandwiches

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Part 01

Motivation and background

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Global burning issues

Energy crisis, air pollution and global warming have been burning issues threatening the existence and development of human society . Power resources should be optimized in response to these bad situations.

Energy crisis

Air pollution

Global warming

The Well-to-Wheel Efficiency Comparison

❖ Crude Oil

Fractional Distillation of Crude Oil

Fractionating column
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❖ Oil Refining

95%

87%

EV 19% in total

ICEV 12% in total

Industrial Development

TESLA MOTORS

Tesla Model S

BMW Group

BMW i3

Mercedes-Benz

Generation EQ

Typical Types of Power Battery Cases

Battery case is the load-bearing part of the power battery pack of electric vehicle, which is usually installed in the bottom of the car body. It is mainly used to protect lithium battery from damage in unexpected accidents.

Sheet metal

- High strength
- Easy to process
- Weight of mass

Die-casting

- Anti-aging
- Fire resistance
- Light-weight

Composites

- Light-weight
- Corrosion Resistance
- Ageing

Sandwiches

- High stiffness
- Good crashworthiness
- Light-weight

Design of Power Battery Pack for Safety

Safety design of Power Battery system

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Part 02

Low-velocity impact responses

Low-velocity impacting tests

Experimental setup and specimens

Drop-tower system INSTRON/9250HV

- Dynamic load cell
- Velocity transducer
- Displacement sensor

3D optical measuring system to acquire the full-field external deflection

Computerized tomographic scan (C-scan) to detect the internal damage

Effect of face-sheet materials

Typical double-peak responses can be observed for sandwiches with both ductile and brittle facesheets.

(a) Under impact energy of 40J

(b) Under impact energy of penetration

The deflection of the bottom facesheets are more concentrated for sandwiches with FRP facesheets..

Off-plane impacting sketch in battery protecting

Crashworthiness criteria of sandwich panels

Comparison of crashworthiness performances

To evaluate the protecting performances of sandwich panels, three crashworthiness criteria were introduced

- Initial peak load
- Penetration energy
- Specific penetration energy

Finite element (FE) model

Numerical model of sandwich panel

Validation of the numerical model

Compressive test

Shearing test

Tensile test

The finite element (FE) method for predicting impacting response

- Johnson-Cook model for ductile face-sheets
- Homogenized treatment for foam core
- Surface-erosion contact algorithm

The kinetic energy was dissipated and transformed into four parts

- Internal energy of top facesheet
- Internal energy of bottom facesheet
- Internal energy of foam core
- Frictional energy

- Under small-energy impacting, the top facesheet is the main component of energy dissipating (about 64%) .
- Frictional energy can be an important part of energy absorption when penetrated.

Analysis of multi-layered sandwiches based on FE model

Schematic of sandwich panels with multi-layer core

Multi-layered sandwich panels are studied by FE model

- Symmetric
- Equal-weighting
- Equal-thickness of cores
- Equal-thickness of facesheets

There are both advantages and disadvantages of multi-layered sandwich panels

- Higher crush force efficiency
- Lower stiffness

Analytical solution based on energy analysis

Sketch of indentation profile

Membrane stretching of skin

Compression-shearing of core

Deformation of components

The profile assumption for local indentation

$$\begin{cases} \alpha(r) = \sqrt{R_1^2 - r^2} - R_1 + \alpha_0 & 0 \leq r \leq \frac{a}{2} \\ \alpha(r) = R_2 - \sqrt{R_2^2 - (r - a)^2} & \frac{a}{2} \leq r \leq a \end{cases}$$

Minimum potential energy

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \alpha_0} = 0 \Rightarrow P = f(\alpha_0)$$

The potential energy of system

$$\Pi = U_m + U_c + U_s + U_p$$

Where,

$$U_m = 2\pi \int_0^a (N_r \epsilon_r + N_\theta \epsilon_\theta) r dr \quad U_c = 2\pi \int_0^a \int_0^{h_c} q \epsilon_c r dy dr$$

$$U_s = 2\pi \int_0^a \int_0^{h_c} \tau_c \epsilon_s r dy dr \quad U_p = - \int_0^{\alpha_0} P d \alpha_0$$

The response surface of initial peak load can be constructed based on the geometric parameters of sandwich panels. the initial peak load **is more sensitive to the face-sheet thickness**; and it appears a non-linear relationship between the initial peak load and the face-sheet thickness. In addition, the theoretical prediction overestimated the experimental results. On the contrary, the numerical prediction underestimated the actual situation slightly.

2D section plots at $H_c = 15$

Response surface of initial peak load

2D section plots at $T_f = 1.5$

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Part 03

Residual performance

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Quasi-static compression tests

3D DIC system

Experimental setup and specimens

Specimens under various impacting energy

In-panel compressive tests

- Guideway for alignment
- Clamps for end restraint
- Quasi-static load condition

3D digital image correlation (DIC) system to acquire the full-field external deformation

- Charge-coupled device (CCD) cameras
- Symmetrical arrangement
- Picture size at 100 mm × 85 mm

Effect of face-sheet materials

In-panel responses of sandwiches with ductile and brittle face-sheet

Weakening mechanism due to strain differences

The in-panel peak load of sandwiches Al6061 facesheets is higher than those with CFRP facesheets. Although the ultimate strength of Al6061 is lower than CFRP laminates.

Effect of Pre-impact energy

The compressive resistances are greatly weakened after the pre-impact.

Facesheets of pre-impacted specimens deformed locally, and buckled during the initial stage of compression.

The CAI residual properties of sandwich with ductile facesheets are sensitive to the pre-impact energy, and the final residual performance is obviously lower than those with brittle laminated facesheets.

Sandwiches with brittle laminated facesheets can be better choice when considering residual performance in secondary collision.

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Part 04

Concluding remarks

- ❖ Sandwich structures with ductile facesheets have better crashworthiness than those with brittle facesheets, in the off-plane direction.
- ❖ Under in-plane compression, sandwich panels with Al facesheets failed in face-sheet buckling mode. Nevertheless, sandwich panels with laminate facesheets failed in face-sheet fracture mode.
- ❖ Sandwich structures with brittle facesheets have better residual performance than those with brittle facesheets.
- ❖ For the power battery case design, sandwich structures with aluminum/FRP hybrid facesheets can be better choice with overall consideration.

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Part 05

Further work and
expectation

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Further work on the interface

Typical failure modes under in-panel compression load

The interface properties are the key factor of face-sheet buckling.

Climbing drum peel test (ASTM D1781)

The mixed mode bending (MMB) test (Manca, 2012)

Further work on the yield surface of foam materials

Uniaxial load

Biaxial load

Triaxial load

The rate-dependent properties of foam material

The yield/failure behavior of foam materials should be investigated under multi-axial loading .

The rate-dependent properties of foam material should be taken into consideration.

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